

Supplementary material for the paper: Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility in noise and reverberation for normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners

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Supplementary figure 1: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier *et al.* (2012). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models.

Supplementary figure 2: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier and Culling (2008). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models.

Supplementary figure 3: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their first experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models.

Supplementary figure 4: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their third experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. The predictions of the *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as only the BRIRs are taken as input.

Supplementary figure 5: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their fourth experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the room-independent version of the proposed model and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models.

Supplementary figure 6: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Cueille et al. (2022). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the version of the proposed model that uses a room-independent ELL and an internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level (as in the *vicente2020* model), and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. The predictions of the *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as only the BRIRs are taken as input.

Supplementary figure 7: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Cueille et al. (2022). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the version of the proposed model that uses a room-independent ELL and an internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum, and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. The predictions of the *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as only the BRIRs are taken as input.

Supplementary figure 8: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Vicente et al. (2021). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the version of the proposed model that uses a room-independent ELL and an internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level (as in the *vicente2020* model), and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. The predictions of the *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as only the BRIRs are taken as input.

Supplementary figure 9: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Vicente et al. (2021). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the version of the proposed model that uses a room-independent ELL and an internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum, and for the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. The predictions of the *leclere2015* model are identical with stationary and modulated noise, as only the BRIRs are taken as input.

Supplementary figure 10: Scatter plots of measured SRTs against predicted SRTs for the HI listeners from Cueille et al. (2022), with the two internal noise calculations. Within each panel the Pearson correlation coefficient and the mean absolute error between measured and predicted SRTs are specified in the upper left corner. The solid lines mark identity between predictions and observations.

Supplementary figure 11: Scatter plots of measured SRTs against predicted SRTs for the HI listeners from Vicente et al. (2021), with the two internal noise calculations. Within each panel the Pearson correlation coefficient and the mean absolute error between measured and predicted SRTs are specified in the upper left corner. The solid lines mark identity between predictions and observations.